

Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Performance: Trust as a Mediator

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Abstract: Research indicates that people trust more in organizations with high organizational support. Employees who perceive organizational support are more committed to their organization and perform better than those who do not perceive support. This study was aimed at investigating the mediating effect of interpersonal trust on the relationship between organizational support and performance. The study was conducted by collecting responses from 174 employees working in 5 leading BPO firms in Pune City. Perceived trust was measured by the Interpersonal Trust Scale, while perceived organizational support and employee performance were measured by Likert based Behavior-Related Measurement System (BRMS). Results showed that only low levels of trust were associated with lower levels of employee performance in both cases (Organizational Support & Employee Performance). On the contrary, high levels of trust were associated with higher levels of both. It means, if employees perceive that their organizations provide them trustful settings to do their work, they will feel more confident and hence perform better.

Keywords: Organizational support, Perceived Trust, employee performance

1. Introduction

Our work is increased through our relationships with others, particularly with those in our organization. This is true in all walks of life, but especially so in the business world. It's an axiom that organizations will benefit from building trust. Trust allows us to build a sense of shared destiny and we achieve greater productivity through better relationships at work - and this goes for both individuals and managers alike. There are two problems: the first simply relates to the question of how performance can be improved by increasing organizational support; the second concerns whether there is evidence to suggest that increases in organizational support lead to increases in employees' perceptions of trust at work. Research has shown that individuals who perceive high levels of organizational

support are more committed to their organization and perform better than those who do not perceive support. But how do managers achieve this? What do they need to do?

The present study was aimed at investigating the mediating effect of perceived interpersonal trust on the relationship between organizational support and performance. The current study assesses the mediating effect of perceived interpersonal trust on the relationship between organizational support and performance. This study focuses on employees working in leading BPO firms in Pune City. The main hypothesis of the current study is that there is an association between perceived organizational support and employee performance in organizations as measured by a BRMS. Both of these measures were also associated with perceived trust. These findings are consistent with previous research because the mediating effect of perceived interpersonal trust on the relationship between organization support and performance can be explained by the concept of trust.

2. Literature Review

There is no direct research on how to increase trust among employees. Trust is a crucial factor that can improve or decrease employee performance (Hirshman, 2004). Organizations have many strategies that are used to increase trust in the employee. It helps employees grow as an individual and work on their potential; it also leads them to stay longer in the same place. However, previous research on organizational support does not explicitly look at the role of trust in communication with employees. It is thought that trust can be generated by the perception of employees. The perception of organizational support is one of the most important factors that employees look for in an organization to develop their performance. Organizational support means employee perceptions about what their organizations provide them with on the job (e.g., managers, material and physical resources). Organizational support as a communication process helps in building trust among employees; it also helps in improving employee performance by improving motivation (Hirshman, 2004).

Employee performance can be considered as a function of its perception by an individual or group. This process can be measured by a Behavior-Related Measurement System (BRMS) (Bass and Bass, 2001). Perceived organizational support has been shown to affect some of the best indicators of employee performance, such as organizational commitment and job satisfaction. The role of perceived organisational support in affecting job performance is closely related to the role of perceived trust. Employees are sensitive about the trust that their managers are building. The perception that each individual has about the individual manager's behavior is closely related to their work motivation. A good employee has a great perception about their manager's trustworthiness and therefore will be more committed to them and perform better (Bass and Bass, 2001).

One of the main reasons for interpersonal trust to be developed is the perception of whether or not an organization trusts its own employees. Organizations should focus on providing employee-oriented support to their people in order to build a sense of interdepartmental trust (Lidz and Miles, 1995). Employees are more likely to accept the organization's values and beliefs if it provides them with sufficient organizational support (Lidz and Miles, 1995). Employees are likely to have a greater commitment to their organizations if they perceive that their organizations provide them with support as required by their job and that they can depend on each other (Angoff, 1988; Lidz and Miles, 1995).

There are various methods that organizations can use to build customer trust. However, there are different ways in which an organization can improve employee performance by providing support. Hiring the best employees is the first and foremost step that is taken by the organization in giving support to them (Lidz and Miles, 1995). Hiring the best employees requires a good selection process. An employee's capability of doing their work is highly related to their work motivation. It also depends on the extent of support they receive from the organization (Lidz and Miles, 1995). The perception of organizational support is strengthened by each level of commitment that employee has towards a company (Angoff, 1988; Lidz and Miles, 1995). Organizations should provide their employees with continuous support by providing them with the required resources and implementing certain policies in order to give an effective communication process (Lidz and Miles, 1995). The effectiveness of the process depends on how much trust is given to the employees. Trust is enhanced by building communication channels and making things clear for each employee (Lidz and Miles, 1995).

Organizational Support: Organizations generally provide an environment that is expected to provide significant help for its employees to perform their job. Organizations may provide employees with "human" resources, money, insurance and other benefits. They also provide employees with a number of decision-making tools, such as job descriptions, performance appraisal systems and decision rights.

Employee Performance: Employee performance is assessed by the success they achieve on various tasks that they perform in their jobs. The success of an employee is considered to be the key indicator of how good he/she is at performing a certain task. When an employee performs well on a certain kind of task, his/her performance is considered as good (Demerouti and Vanhofer, 2003).

The present research assessed the role of perceived organizational trust as a mediator in the relationship between organizational support and employee performance. This study investigates the mediating effect of perceived interpersonal trust on the relationship between organizational support and employee performance. This study focuses on

employees working in leading BPO firms in Pune City. The primary focus is on how individual perceptions of trust are influenced by several factors, including organizational "support".

3. Methodology

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- Identify a sample of 174 employees from leading BPO Firms using convenience sampling (organizations were having their offices within the limits of the Pune Municipal Corporation)
- Design and validate a (minimum 10-point) questionnaire for ascertainment of
 - 1) The Interpersonal Trust Scale is used to assess one's belief that other people's actions, promises, or (verbal or written) claims may be trusted. 25-item Likert-type scale (and 15 filler items). The Rotter Interpersonal Trust Scale is another name for the Rotter Interpersonal Trust Scale (1967)
 - 2) Level of perceived organizational Support (20 items)
 - 3) Level of Employee performance (10 items)
 - 4) Seek responses on a 5-point Likert scale
 - 5) Conduct the survey
 - 6) Summarize the responses
 - 7) Apply multiple regression analysis and check the mediating role of the concerned variable.
 - 8) Analyze the results

The hypotheses set in this regard were as under:

Ho1: Interpersonal trust does not play a mediating role between perceived organizational support and employee performance.

Ha1: Interpersonal trust plays a mediating role between perceived organizational support and employee performance.

The study was conducted across 2 IT parks (Magarpatta, Rajiv Gandhi Infotech Park) that host work-centres of the 5 leading BPOs that have been considered for the purpose of the current study.

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

Responses were collected under 4 sections:

- 1) First section of the questionnaire was dedicated to the profile information of the employees.
- 2) Second section (Scale) was dedicated to measure the Interpersonal Trust.
- 3) Third section gathered responses for the Level of perceived organizational support.

- 4) Fourth section gathered responses for measuring the level of Employee Performance.

For each of the sections an average/ scores were calculated.

- 1) Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire were averaged to get a single score for that section,
- 2) The section-wise average score was considered for the purpose of conducting a multiple regression analysis using suitable macros by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D.
- 3) P-values were calculated, and the null hypotheses was checked for rejection or non-rejection.

Cronbach’s alpha score for the questionnaire was calculated the results have been discussed in the next section of the paper.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the values of Cronbach’s alpha were above 0.7 in each of the cases. This shows the level of internal consistency and proves the validity of the measures that have been calculated.

Table 1: Results of the Cronbach’s Alpha

Sr. No.	Section of the questionnaire	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha value
1	Rotter Interpersonal Trust Scale	40	0.822
2	Level of perceived organizational support	15	0.813
3	Employee Performance	10	0.791
4	Complete Questionnaire	65	0.781

Table 2 shows that the value of the coefficient (between Level of perceived organizational support and Employee Performance is 0.6582 and it is significant at the 0.01 level.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model Results						
R .7007	R-sq .4910	MSE .1061	F 165.9398	df1 1	df2 172	p .0000
Model						
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	1.1575	.1792	6.4608	.0000	.8039	1.5111
Support	.6582	.0511	12.8818	.0000	.5573	.7590

Table 3 shows that without Interpersonal Trust, the relationship between Level of perceived organizational support and Employee Performance is not significant.

Table 3: Model Summary

R	R-sq.	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.3449	.1189	.2359	11.5429	2	171	.0000
Model	coeff	se	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
constant 1	.9822	.2978	6.6553	.0000	1.3943	2.5701
Support	.0804	.1068	.7525	.4528	-.1305	.2912
Trust	.3250	.1137	2.8582	.0048	.1006	.5495

Table 4: Total effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c'_cs
.2943	.0778	3.784	.0002	.1408	.4478	.2772

Direct effect of X on Y						
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c'_cs
.0804	.1068	.7525	.4528	-.1305	.2912	.0757

Table 4 shows that the total effect of X on Y is significant ($p < 0.05$). However, the Direct Effect of X on Y is not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Indirect effect(s) of X on Y

Variable	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Trust	0.2139	0.0954	0.0306	0.4044

From table 5, we can see that the lower limit confidence interval (0.0306) and the upper limit confidence interval (0.4044) do not include 0 in the indirect effects of X on Y suggesting that there is a significant mediating effect of the variable ‘Interpersonal Trust’. This leads us to accept that Interpersonal trust plays a mediating role between perceived organizational support and employee performance.

5. Conclusion

Interpersonal trust plays a mediating role between perceived organizational support and employee performance. This can happen as Employees who have a high level of interpersonal trust will experience higher levels of perceived organizational support and satisfaction. They also perform better than their peers who experience a lower level of interpersonal trust. Interpersonal trust has been linked to job engagement and employee performance. Employee performance is usually measured in terms of work engagement and work performance. Through these measurements we can determine how trusting relationships affect employee performance, through job engagement or job satisfaction. This suggests that interpersonal trust plays a mediating role between perceived organizational support and employee performance. When a person views their organization as trustworthy they will be more likely to feel a sense of organizational support. This has been proven to be true in the workplace. When employees trust their

organizations they will have higher levels of perceived organizational support. Research has shown that employee performance is enhanced with increased levels of perceived organizational support, as it relates to job engagement and job satisfaction.

The level of interpersonal trust that an employee holds towards their organization can also be linked to the level of job satisfaction and amount of job performance an individual delivers within an organization. In the past, analysis of employee engagement has shown that interpersonal trust plays a key role in overall engagement, as well as individual performance within the workplace. There are many organizations who promote the level of trust that employees may have for their organization. This can be seen through many different forms such as company newsletters, feedback forms, and other forms that show work performance improvement areas. Organizations also try to promote their values to be displayed in their organizations by actively recruiting from a wide variety of different social groups.

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